

APPLICATION OF COPPER AS A DIFFUSION MEDIUM
FOR FORMATION OF CHROMIUM CARBIDES ON CARBON FIBERS

A. Miyase

and

K. Piekarski

Dept. of Mechanical Engineering
University of Waterloo
Waterloo, Ontario N2L, 3G1, Canada

INTRODUCTION

Carbon (graphite) fiber is one of the most attractive fibers as a reinforcing material for metals because of its high specific properties, good retention of its properties at elevated temperatures in an inert atmosphere, and its reasonable price. Although the outlook for graphite fiber reinforced metal matrix composites is very promising, the fiber has one major drawback which retards the development of the composite system. Most metals which can be used for structural elements have either high solubility of carbon or reactivity with carbon; hence it is very difficult to obtain thermally stable and strong interfaces. In order to overcome these, the application of suitable carbide coating on the fibers would be the simplest and the most advantageous.

Chromium is commercially readily available and can easily be electroplated. It forms a stable and reasonably impervious carbide and it can be well bonded to a metallic matrix. Thus, in this research a chromium carbide coating on carbon fibers was investigated.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The fibers used in this study are commercially available high strength and high elastic modulus graphitized carbon fibers under the trade name of Fortafil 6T from Great Lakes Carbon Corporation, having dumb-bell or dog-bone shape cross section.

Fibers were first cleaned of any organic substances by passing them through a furnace at 850°C, containing an argon atmosphere. Then plating was carried out for a predetermined period of time and in various sequences. The plating solutions employed for copper, nickel and chromium coatings were copper sulfate bath, the Watt's bath and high chromic acid concentration sulfate bath, respectively.

After plating, the fibers were heated approximately to 1100°C in five minutes and cooled down. The total heat treatment period was about 15 minutes. Specimens were prepared by conventional metallographic techniques and observed by an optical microscope.

1(a)

1(b)

Fig.1 Ni-Cr Coated Fiber (a)Before Heat Treatment (b)After Heat Treatment

RESULTS

Because of the difficulties of the direct deposition of chromium on carbon fibers, fibers were first plated with approximately $1\ \mu\text{m}$ thick nickel coating, and then overcoated with chromium. Figures 1-a and 1-b show the photomicrographs of nickel-chromium coated fibers in as-coated condition and after heat treatment respectively. Carbide formation reaction is not uniform and the interface between formed carbides and the fiber unreacted is irregular.

In the second experiments fibers were preplated with copper. Since some difficulties were also experienced to obtain a uniform copper plating, nickel flash undercoating of approximately $0.1\ \mu\text{m}$ thickness was applied before copper-chromium duplex coating. Figures 2-a and 2-b show the morphological changes of nickel-copper-chromium coated fibers as result of the same heat treatment. Fig. 2-b shows carbide formation of approximately $0.7\ \mu\text{m}$. The formed carbide is quite uniform and the boundary between unreacted region of a fiber and the carbide is smooth.

2(b)

Fig.2 Ni-Cu-Cr Coated Fiber (a)Before Heat Treatment (b)After Heat Treatment

The effect of copper overcoating on nickel-copper chromium coated fibers on carbide layer thickness was also examined. After heat treatment, fibers were fused together and formed a mini composite material. The results are shown in Figures 3-a and 3-b. Each fiber is surrounded by uniformly formed thin carbide layer of about $0.5 \mu\text{m}$ thickness and the interface between the fiber and carbide coating is smooth.

DISCUSSION

a) Ni-Cr Coated Fibers:

In the course of compatibility studies of graphite fibers with metallic matrices, Jackson [1] found the formation of chromium carbide (Cr_3C_2) in nickel chromium coated graphite fibers after heat treatment, and the micro-structural changes observed by this experiment showed good agreement with

3(a)

3(b)

Fig.3. Ni-Cu-Cr-Cu Coated Fiber (a)Before Heat Treatment (b)After Heat Treatment

his results. The formation of chromium carbides with irregular interface is considered to be caused by simultaneous diffusion of carbon and chromium into nickel. However, the large difference between diffusion coefficient of carbon into nickel (approximately 3.2×10^{-7} cm²/sec at 1000°C [2]) and inter-diffusion coefficient of chromium into nickel (approximately 1.2×10^{-11} cm²/sec at 1000°C for 0 to 40 atomic percent chromium concentration range[3]) left porosity in carbide layer, as can be seen in Figure 1-b. On the basis of the above observations, this method was abandoned.

b) Ni-Cu-Cr and Ni-Cu-Cr-Cu Coated Fibers:

The formation of uniform carbide layer around graphite fibers and smooth interfacial conditions between them are considered to be the results of insolubility of carbon in metal coating. Above the melting temperature of copper, phenomena are almost the same as with the liquid metal transfer agent technique [4,5]. Liquid copper can work as a transfer agent of chromium since chromium is soluble in copper, but carbon is not.

The kinetics of carbide layer growth was inferred from the growth rate data by Naidichi and Kolesuichenko [6], and by Mortimer and co-workers [7] on carbon - Cu (CR) alloy. Parabolic growth rates of carbide layer formation were recalculated and replotted as a function of temperature in Figure 4, together with carbide layer growth rates measured by Fries et al [8] in carbon-pure chromium diffusion couple. In the analysis by Mortimer et al [7], it was concluded that growth rates increase continuously across melting temperature of copper. However, it appears that there is a discontinuity or a transition zone in growth rates. Since the rate of growth of carbide is parabolic, diffusion mechanism must control the process. The variation of diffusion coefficient of chromium in copper with temperature are shown in Table 1. The ratios of diffusion coefficient of chromium in copper to that of carbon in chromium carbide jump up about two orders of magnitude across the melting temperature of copper, the available chromium for carbide formation is scarce, and consequently the carbon richest chromium carbide (Cr_3C_2) formation is dominant; however, above the melting temperature of copper, chromium supply becomes large enough to form Cr_7C_3 and $Cr_{23}C_6$. As a result the whole phenomenon becomes very similar to that observed in carbon-pure chromium diffusion couple. This consideration is also supported by the observation of Cr_7C_3 and Cr_3C_2 by Naidichi and Kolesuichenko [6] in their experiment. The formation of free energies of three kinds of carbides in the temperature range in which we are interested are very close to each other, thus forming carbides in a system can be varied depending on the availability of chromium or carbon.

TABLE 1 Variation of Diffusion Coefficients of Cr in Cu(Cr) Alloy and of C in Cr_3C_2 , and their Ratios with Temperatures.

Temperature (°C)	Interdiffusion Coefficient \bar{D} (cm ² /sec) Cr in Cu-Cr Alloy*	Chemical Diffusion D (cm ² /sec) C in Cr_3C_2 **	Ratio $D_{Cr} \rightarrow Cu(Cr)$ $D_c \rightarrow Cr_2C_2$
950	2.50×10^{-9}	3.16×10^{-11}	0.79×10^2
995	5.04×10^{-9}	6.05×10^{-11}	0.83×10^2
1050	1.12×10^{-8}	1.29×10^{-10}	0.86×10^2
1150	Cr in Liquid Cu*** 3.34×10^{-6}	4.17×10^{-10}	0.80×10^4
1200	3.69×10^{-6}	7.09×10^{-10}	0.52×10^4
1250	4.03×10^{-6}	1.17×10^{-9}	0.34×10^4

* Ref. 9.
** Calculated from the results in Ref. 8.
*** Ref. 10.

Fig. 4

CONCLUSION

Using chemical reaction process, graphite fibers were successfully coated by chromium carbides. However, because of the difficulty of direct chromium plating on fibers, some conductive metal coating was required. The success of a uniform and intimate chromium carbide coating depends on the carbon solubility in metals. The metals which have high carbon solubility at elevated temperatures caused simultaneous occurrence of carbon dissolution and carbides formation reaction, and as a result, formed carbides have irregular interfaces between carbides and retained graphite fibers. Metals like copper, however, which have little solubility of carbon at elevated temperatures performed just as a chromium transfer agent to fiber surface, and consequently a smooth and intimate carbide layer was formed around fibers.

REFERENCES

1. Jackson, P.W., "Some Studies of the Compatibility of Graphite and Other Fibers with Metal Matrices," *Met. E. Quarterly*, Vol. 9(3) 1969, p.22.
2. Lander, J.J., Kern, H.E., and Beach, A.L., "Solubility and Diffusion Coefficient of Carbon in Nickel: Reaction Rates of Nickel-Carbon Alloy with Barium Oxide," *J. Appl. Phys.*, Vol.23, 1952, p.1305.
3. Ugaste, Yu.E., "Mutual Diffusion in the System Ni-Cr," *Phys. Metals and Metallography*, Vol. 24, 1967, p.57.
4. Fleming, R.A., and Carter, G.F., "Diffusion Coatings Formed in Molten Calcium Systems, II Variables in the System Ca-Cr-Fe," Corrosion by Liquid Metals, Draley, J.E., and Weeks, J.R., eds., Plenum, New York, 1970, p.305.
5. Rashid, M.S., and Wirkus, C.D., "Development of Carbide Coatings for Graphite Filaments," *Amer. Ceramic Soc. Bulletin*, Vol. 51 (11), 1972, p.836.
6. Naidichi, Y.V., and Kolesuichenko, "Investigation of the Wetting of Diamond and Graphite by Molten Metals and Alloys, V. Carbide Formation Kinetics at the Graphite/Metallic Melt Interface," *Sov. Metall. Met. Ceramics*, (2), 1968, p.139.
7. Mortimer, D.A., Nicholas, M.G., and Crispin, R.M., "The Compatibility of Carbon with Copper Alloys Containing Chromium, Titanium, or Vanadium," *Int. Conf. on Carbon Fibers, Their Place in Modern Technology*, The Plastics Institute, London, Feb. 1974, Paper No.15, p.101.
8. Fries, R.F., Cummingd, J.E., Hoffman, C.G., and Daily, S.A., "The Chemical Diffusion of Carbon in the Group VI Metal Carbides," 6th Plansee Seminar on "High Temperature Materials," Benesovsky, F., Ed., 1968, p.597.
9. Youdelis, W.V., and Wu, H.Y., "Interdiffusion in Copper (rich)-Chromium Solid Solutions," *Can. Metall. Quarterly*, Vol 14, 1975, p.315.
10. Shurygin, P.M., and Shantarin, V.D., "Diffusion of Metals in Molten Copper," *Phys. Metals and Metallography*, Vol. 16, 1963, p.81.

SESSION 3:
FATIGUE AND FRACTURE:
ANALYSIS, TEST AND PREVENTION-I

CHAIRMAN:

L.M. Lackman,
Mail Zone 011-AB64
Rockwell International Corp.
International Airport
Los Angeles, CA 90009

CO-CHAIRMAN:

N.J. Parratt
Explosives R&D Establishment
Waltham Abbey
Essex En9 IBP, United Kingdom

